

INTERRELATIONSHIP OF READING MOTIVATION, HABITS, AND TEACHING STRATEGIES IN SHAPING STUDENTS' LITERARY APPRECIATION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Literary appreciation is a foundational component of secondary English education, fostering critical thinking, interpretive competence, and contextual engagement with texts. There is a clear gap in empirical evidence on how these three factors jointly influence students' literary appreciation. Grounded in Self-Determination Theory, this descriptive-correlational study examined the predictive influence of reading motivation, reading habits, and teachers' instructional strategies on the literary appreciation skills of 152 Grade 11 students in a large national high school in the Division of Misamis Oriental during the 2025–2026 academic year. Data were collected using adapted Likert-type questionnaires assessing reading motivation, reading habits, and perceptions of instructional strategies, along with a 30-item multiple-choice test measuring literary appreciation through textual analysis, interpretation, and contextual understanding. Descriptive statistics (weighted mean and standard deviation) and multiple regression analysis were employed. Findings revealed high levels of reading motivation, moderate reading habits characterized by greater reliance on digital materials, and strong perceptions of teachers' instructional strategies. Literary appreciation skills were generally high, with interpretation emerging as the strongest domain, while textual analysis and contextual understanding were comparatively moderate. Regression results indicated that reading motivation and teachers' instructional strategies significantly predicted literary appreciation skills, whereas reading habits did not. Future research may employ longitudinal or experimental designs to establish causal relationships among motivational constructs, instructional interventions, and outcomes of literary appreciation, thereby strengthening evidence-based practices in secondary literature instruction.

Reading motivation and targeted instructional strategies, such as scaffolding, directly enhance literary appreciation skills, such as interpretation and analysis, whereas unguided reading frequency does not.

Keywords: *reading motivations, habits, teaching strategies, literary appreciation skills*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is an essential part of formal schooling, but in many modern classrooms, students' interaction with literary texts is challenged by competing academic demands, limited reading time, and varying levels of motivation. Reading is a key domain in which learners learn about language, construct meaning, and engage with texts critically, but the capacity to appreciate literature is frequently unevenly developed among students. Literary appreciation affords students the ability to analyze, interpret, and evaluate literary texts in terms of meaning, styles, and techniques (Chamber 2022), characteristics shaped not only by students' cognitive capacities but also by reading motivation, habitual practices, and instructional experiences.

In this context, students' reading motivation and reading habits, as well as teachers' strategies, emerge as important but unevenly aligned factors. Most students exhibit at least initial interest in reading but are not regularly involved in the practice due to academic obligations and limited access to literature beyond what they are required to read. Reading motivation provides the impetus for engagement (Wasilewsky, 2023), while reading habits transform that motivation into a sustained reading practice that advances comprehension and interpretation. In practice, though, motivated students don't always develop strong reading habits, and teachers often prioritise curriculum coverage over engaging with the literature because of time and scope constraints. Improving students' engagement in reading literature through flexible, student-centered strategies has been achieved (Mente, 2022; Rishit, 2024), but the actual effectiveness of these strategies depends heavily on how students come to view and respond to them in practice.

Despite recognition of these realities, existing research highlights significant empirical gaps. First, most of the literature on reading motivation, reading habits, and teaching strategies has treated them as separate predictors of literacy outcomes, providing little information about their interrelations in real-life instructional settings (Haiyan, 2023). Second, (and linked to the first point), there is a lack of empirical consideration of students' perceptions of teachers' literature-teaching strategies and how these perceptions interact with motivational and behavioral factors to shape skills in literary appreciation (Oke, 2024). These deficits are felt acutely in places where literature instruction must billow between curricular right and left, students' disparate levels of interest, access, and reading ability.

In response to these contextual and empirical voids, the present research explores the reciprocal influence of reading motivation, reading habits, and teachers' strategies employed in teaching literature on students' literary appreciation skills. The originality of

this study lies in its integrative, context-sensitive approach, which allows us to understand how motivational, behavioral, and instructional factors work together rather than as isolated elements in real classroom environments. A focus on students' experiences and perceptions places the study in productive tension with dominant views of literature teaching, offering a more nuanced picture of how literary appreciation is enacted. This resonates with Sileris' (2023) argument that learners from diverse motivational and experiential backgrounds may approach the same literary texts in very different ways.

The study advances a more integrated model of literary appreciation as the outcome of interactions between learner and contextual factors relevant at all levels of analysis. In practical terms, it offers data-driven guidance to teachers and school leaders seeking to develop a responsive approach to literature instruction grounded in students' motivational profiles and reading behaviors. These findings reinforce a more intentional and contextually grounded literature pedagogy by Balones et al. Al. (2021) elucidates how teaching strategies intersect with students' motivation and habits. In addition, the study aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) in addressing ongoing challenges related to student belongingness, literacy development, and equitable access to quality education (United Nations Statistics Division, 2023). Fostering students' appreciation for literature bolsters not just academic success, but the home-building of interpretative and critical skills that can serve throughout a lifetime of learning.

Research Questions

This descriptive-correlational study aimed to determine significant correlations among reading motivations, reading habits, teachers' strategies for teaching literature, and students' literary appreciation skills. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the participants' self-reports of their reading motivation?
2. What are the participants' levels of reading habits?
3. What are the participants' assessments of their teachers' strategy in teaching literature?
4. What are the participants' levels of literary appreciation skills in terms of:
 - 4.1. Textual Analysis;
 - 4.2. Interpretation; and
 - 4.3. Contextual Understanding?
5. Are the participants' reading motivation, reading habits, assessment of their teachers' strategy in teaching literature significantly influenced by their literary appreciation skills?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan can be recommended?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, a descriptive-correlational research design was used to determine the correlation between reading motivations, reading habits, and teachers' strategies in

teaching literature and students' literary appreciation skills. This allows the study to use descriptive correlational methods to achieve its goals by determining the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable without manipulation.

The participants in this study were Grade 11 students currently enrolled in the specialized subject "Creative Writing" for the second semester of the academic year 2025-2026. Before actual data collection, the researcher obtained ethical clearance from the graduate school's Institutional Ethics Review Committee, ensuring that all research protocols complied with ethical standards for human research. As stated in RA 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal data/information has been collected for valid purposes. Furthermore, the distributed and collected data have been coded to protect participants' identities. The names, cellphone numbers, and email addresses of the participants were not collected at the time the participants answered the form, in line with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). Instead of the participant's name, the researcher assigned a unique code number, which was written on the questionnaires and test papers. All data collected has been treated with strict confidentiality, and upon completion of the study and encoding, the soft copies have been permanently deleted, while the hard copies have been properly disposed of after the data acquired from the participants has been fulfilled. Thus, the researcher secured an assent form from the research participants, and the informed consent of their parents/guardians was attached.

A "lottery-based sampling procedure," a simple random sampling method, has been employed to select the desired participants for this study. All Grade 11 HUMSS students in the big school of Alubijid District who are who are enrolled to the current academic year were identified as participants in the study, for a total population of 252 students. Only 155 students have been selected as the sample for this study based on Taro Yamane's sample size formula. However, of the initial sample of 155 students, 152 were included in the analysis after three outliers were excluded.

For the Reading motivation survey questionnaire, the researcher adapted the "Reading Motivation Questionnaire" developed by Guthrie and Wigfield and translated into Turkish by Yıldız, as cited in the study by Bakkaloğlu (2022). For the reading habits questionnaire, the researcher adapted and used a modified version of the "Reading Behaviors Questionnaire (RBQ)" that was used in a prior dissertation and served as the main tool for gathering data. Moreover, the survey questionnaire used to determine the strategies employed by the teachers in teaching literature was a checklist questionnaire adapted from Rashid et. al. (2010) and subsequently used in the study by Simene (2017).

Moreover, the researcher used a self-developed questionnaire comprising 30 multiple-choice items. The 30 items were divided into 3 categories: 10 for textual analysis, 10 for interpretation, and 10 for contextual understanding of the participants, for a total of 30 items. The construct of the questions was based on the framework of Ribeiro's (2025) study about literary appreciation. The validity of the instruments used in this study was established by the panel, and the materials were pilot-tested for reliability.

In treating the data of this study, the following statistical tools has been used by the researcher: For the research question 1,2,3 and 4, the researcher used descriptive statistics such as weighted mean, standard deviation and frequency distribution in determining the level of reading motivations of the participants, perceived level of reading habits, teachers' strategy in teaching literature and the Level of literary appreciation skills of the students. In research question no. 5, to determine if there is a significant relationship in the participants' reading motivation, reading habits, assessment of their teachers' strategy in teaching literature significantly influences their literary appreciation skills, the researcher used regression analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the participants' self-report of their reading motivation?

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation of the participants' self-reported reading motivation. The overall mean of 2.77 (SD = 0.48) falls within the range of 2.51–3.50, interpreted as High, corresponding to the descriptor “a little like me.” This indicates that participants generally identify with the motivational statements in a consistent and personally meaningful way, though not with maximal intensity. This suggests moderately internalized motivation rather than strong or highly self-determined endorsement (Bureau et al. 2022). The relatively low standard deviation reflects homogeneity in responses. Most participants (67.11%) were classified as having High motivation, followed by 26.97% with Low motivation, 5.26% with Very High motivation, and 0.66% with Very Low motivation.

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Self-reports of their Reading Motivation

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
3.51 - 4.00	A lot like me	Very High	8	5.26
2.51 - 3.50	A little like me	High	102	67.11
1.51 - 2.50	A little different from me	Low	41	26.97
1.00 - 1.50	Very different from me	Very Low	1	0.66
Total			152	100.0
Overall Mean			2.77	
Interpretation			High	
SD			0.48	

Specific Indicators	M	Description	SD
1. I often visit the library to borrow books to read at home.	1.64	Very different from me	0.84

2.	I believe I will do well in reading next year.	2.89	A little like me	0.85
3.	I read because I enjoy learning new things important for my studies.	2.93	A little like me	0.85
4.	My friends and family sometimes recognize me as a good reader.	2.66	A little like me	0.89
5.	I learn more from reading compared to some of my classmates.	2.49	A little different from me	0.81
6.	I feel proud when my teacher or parents recognize my progress in reading.	3.05	A little like me	0.90
7.	I like hearing positive feedback about my reading abilities.	3.08	A little like me	0.90
8.	Grades are important to me to see how I am doing in reading.	3.12	A little like me	0.89
9.	I sometimes help my friends with their schoolwork in reading.	2.45	A little different from me	0.89
10.	I try to finish every reading assignment and submit my work on time.	2.69	A little like me	0.96
11.	I prefer reading when the material is not too difficult to understand.	2.95	A little like me	0.93
12.	I sometimes read to my siblings or parents at home.	2.07	A little different from me	0.97
13.	My friends and I enjoy sharing or exchanging books and stories.	2.18	A little different from me	0.99
14.	I am willing to put effort into improving my reading skills.	3.30	A little like me	0.83
15.	I am interested in reading topics about real-life people and experiences.	3.14	A little like me	0.96
16.	I read about my hobbies or interests to learn more about them.	2.96	A little like me	0.98
17.	I enjoy reading fiction (such as adventure, fantasy, or mystery stories).	3.07	A little like me	1.05
18.	I like to learn new information about topics that interest me.	3.16	A little like me	0.84
19.	I enjoy making connections from stories to my own life or sharing them with friends.	2.89	A little like me	0.89
20.	If I am reading something interesting, I sometimes lose track of time.	2.78	A little like me	0.93

The analysis of the data reveals the key reading behaviors among students, as reflected in the top five highest mean scores. The highest mean, “I am willing to put effort into improving my reading skills” (M = 3.3, SD = 0.83), indicates that students are most committed to improving their reading abilities, showing a clear interest in self-improvement. This is closely followed by their strong desire, “I like to learn new information about topics that interest me.” (M = 3.16, SD = 0.84), demonstrating an academic motivation to seek out knowledge. Students also expressed a notable interest: “I am interested in reading topics about real-life people and experiences.” (M = 3.14, SD = 0.96), which suggests an inclination toward practical and relatable content. Grades are important to students as an indicator of their reading progress. “Grades are important to me to see how I am doing in reading.” (M = 3.12, SD = 0.89), further emphasizing their focus on measurable achievement. Lastly, students enjoy hearing positive feedback: “I like hearing positive feedback about my reading abilities.” (M = 3.08, SD = 0.90), highlighting the role of encouragement in motivating reading habits (Widyaningsih & Nugroho, 2025). These findings are consistent with recent studies showing that students with higher intrinsic and extrinsic reading motivation are more engaged and persistent in literacy tasks (Guthrie & McRae, 2021).

In contrast, the five lowest indicators point to areas where student engagement is limited. The lowest mean score, “I often visit the library to borrow books to read at home” (M = 1.64, SD = 0.84) suggests that visiting the library to borrow books is a rare activity among students, indicating a lack of proactive involvement in independent reading. Following closely is the infrequent practice “I sometimes read to my siblings or parents at home.” (M = 2.07, SD = 0.97), which points to minimal family reading engagement.

The exchange of books and stories with peers, “My friends and I enjoy sharing or exchanging books and stories.” (M = 2.18, SD = 0.99), is also not a common behavior, reflecting limited social reading interaction. Additionally, students rarely help their friends with reading schoolwork. “I sometimes help my friends with their schoolwork in reading.” (M = 2.45, SD = 0.89), suggesting that collaborative reading support is minimal. Finally, the lower score “I learn more from reading compared to some of my classmates.” (M = 2.49, SD = 0.81) indicates that students may not perceive reading as giving them a comparative academic advantage. These patterns align with recent research highlighting that low participation in social and voluntary reading activities can negatively influence overall reading engagement and literacy development (Kim & Ramineni, 2022).

Research Question 2. What are the participants’ levels of reading habits?

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants’ reading habits. The overall mean of 3.08 (SD = 0.64) indicates that the participants’ reading habits are generally moderate. This suggests that learners engage in reading with some regularity, though such engagement is not consistently sustained across different text types or purposes.

The relatively low standard deviation indicates fairly consistent responses among participants, suggesting similar reading patterns within the group. Consistent with the

literature, moderate reading habits often reflect situational and task-driven engagement, particularly in academic settings where reading is shaped by access and instructional demands rather than personal inclination (Abid et al., 2023).

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Levels of Reading Habits

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Always	Very High	2	1.32
3.51-4.50	Very often	High	37	24.34
2.51-3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	85	55.92
1.51-2.50	Rarely	Low	28	18.42
1.00-1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0
Total			152	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation			3.08	
SD			Moderate	
			0.64	

Specific Indicators participants' reading habits

<i>I currently read...</i>	M	Description	SD
1. for leisure.	2.81	Sometimes	1.13
2. for academic purposes.	3.74	Very often	0.97
3. for informational purposes.	3.54	Very often	0.96
4. books with illustrations	3.05	Sometimes	1.03
5. young adult literature.	2.63	Sometimes	1.01
6. fiction.	3.45	Sometimes	1.23
7. non-fiction.	3.07	Sometimes	1.06
8. poetry.	3.03	Sometimes	1.24
9. drama/plays.	3.40	Sometimes	1.24
10. magazines.	2.13	Rarely	1.09
11. newspapers.	1.82	Rarely	1.03
12. online.	4.11	Very often	1.06
13. religious material.	3.28	Sometimes	1.17

An examination of the indicators reveals the dominant and least practiced reading behaviors. The five highest mean scores highlight reading activities that are largely functional and accessible. Reading online obtained the highest mean ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 1.06$), indicating that participants very often engage with digital texts. This reflects the centrality of online platforms in students' academic and everyday lives. Reading for academic purposes ranked second ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.97$), followed by reading for informational purposes ($M = 3.54$, $SD = 0.96$), suggesting that reading is frequently driven by school-related and practical information needs. Reading drama or plays ($M = 3.40$, $SD = 1.24$) and reading religious materials ($M = 3.28$, $SD = 1.17$) also fell within the higher range, though still interpreted as "sometimes," indicating occasional but not sustained engagement with these text types. Collectively, these top indicators suggest that

participants' reading habits are oriented toward digital, academic, and purpose-driven texts rather than consistent literary exploration.

In contrast, the five lowest indicators point to limited engagement with certain print and literary forms. Reading newspapers had the lowest mean ($M = 1.82$, $SD = 1.03$), followed by magazines ($M = 2.13$, $SD = 1.09$), both rated "rarely," indicating minimal interaction with traditional print media. Reading young adult literature ($M = 2.63$, $SD = 1.01$) and reading for leisure ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 1.13$) were also among the lower indicators, suggesting limited voluntary and pleasure-oriented reading. Reading books with illustrations ($M = 3.05$, $SD = 1.03$), although interpreted as "sometimes," ranked near the bottom, indicating that such materials are not regularly accessed by participants. The relatively consistent standard deviations across these indicators suggest a shared pattern of infrequent engagement. These trends align with broader evidence of declining print readership and reduced leisure reading among adolescents, alongside a growing preference for shorter and digitally mediated texts (De Vera, 2024).

The findings indicate that while participants demonstrate moderate reading habits, their engagement is concentrated in digital and academic contexts, with limited participation in voluntary, print-based, and leisure reading. This pattern provides important context for understanding why reading habits, measured primarily by frequency and type, may not strongly support deeper literary appreciation, highlighting the need for instructional strategies that encourage reflective and interpretive engagement with texts (Pelletier et al. 2025).

Research Question 3. What are the participants' assessments of their teachers' strategy in teaching literature?

Table 3 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' assessments of their teachers' strategies for teaching literature. The overall mean of 3.20 ($SD = 0.49$) indicates a generally high level of perceived instructional support. This suggests that, overall, participants consistently observe their teachers using a range of strategies in literature lessons. The relatively low standard deviation further indicates that these perceptions are shared by most participants, pointing to common instructional practices rather than isolated classroom experiences. Previous studies have noted that consistent instructional guidance in literature classes is commonly associated with students' engagement and comprehension, although the strength and form of this relationship may vary across contexts (Alqahtani, 2024).

The frequency distribution aligns with this interpretation. A significant proportion of participants (65.79%) reported that the strategies were observed "sometimes", while nearly a third (28.95%) reported observing them "always". A small number of participants (5.26%) perceived the strategies as used 'rarely,' and none reported them as used 'never.' This distribution suggests that the teaching strategies are generally used in literature instruction, with most participants reporting their regular use, though their frequency may vary.

Table 3

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessments of Their Teachers' Strategy in Teaching Literature

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
3.51 - 4.00	Always	Very High	44	28.95
2.51 - 3.50	Sometimes	High	100	65.79
1.51 - 2.50	Rarely	Low	8	5.26
1.00 - 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			152	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation SD				3.20 High 0.49

Specific Indicators for the participant's assessments of their teachers' strategy in teaching literature

	M	Description	SD
<i>Our teacher...</i>			
1. guides us to infer meanings from clues/context in the text.	3.23	Sometimes	0.76
2. encourages us to read between the lines and make implications.	3.27	Sometimes	0.75
3. asks us to predict what happens next in the story.	3.00	Sometimes	0.83
4. guides us to express and justify their opinions on the text.	3.24	Sometimes	0.71
5. sets and uses clear, level-appropriate language activities in lessons.	3.25	Sometimes	0.82
6. provides both original and paraphrased versions of texts for better understanding.	3.18	Sometimes	0.80
7. explains figurative and ambiguous language in simple terms.	3.20	Sometimes	0.82
8. re-tells or summarizes the story to assist understanding.	3.41	Always	0.79
9. provides background information to aid comprehension.	3.28	Always	0.77
10. guides us in identifying and discussing literary elements (e.g., character, setting, theme).	3.50	Always	0.75
11. gets information and responses from students about the text.	3.23	Sometimes	0.76
12. checks our knowledge and understanding through targeted questions.	3.38	Always	0.65
13. relates the theme or content of texts to our personal experiences.	3.18	Sometimes	0.76
14. encourages comparing texts with previously read materials.	2.88	Sometimes	0.75

15.asks us to express our feelings or values about issues raised in texts.	3.03	Sometimes	0.85
16.incorporates and discusses moral lessons and values from the texts.	3.06	Sometimes	0.85
17.directly teaches moral values, when appropriate, from selected texts.	3.13	Sometimes	0.79
18.raises students' awareness of values from texts through discussion.	3.20	Sometimes	0.73
19.uses group/class discussions to deepen interpretation of texts.	3.03	Sometimes	0.86
20.provides written and oral tasks to support literature appreciation.	3.39	Always	0.78

An analysis of the individual indicators shows that the seven highest-rated strategies largely reflect direct instructional guidance and comprehension support. The highest mean score was obtained for guiding students in identifying and discussing literary elements such as character, setting, and theme ($M = 3.50$, $SD = 0.75$), indicating that explicit teaching of core literary concepts is a consistent classroom practice. Other highly rated strategies include retelling or summarizing texts to aid understanding ($M = 3.41$, $SD = 0.79$), providing written and oral tasks to support literary appreciation ($M = 3.39$, $SD = 0.78$), checking students' understanding through targeted questions ($M = 3.38$, $SD = 0.65$), providing background information to support comprehension ($M = 3.28$, $SD = 0.77$), encouraging students to read between the lines ($M = 3.27$, $SD = 0.75$), and setting clear, level-appropriate language activities ($M = 3.25$, $SD = 0.82$). Taken together, these indicators suggest that teachers emphasize structured explanation, guided interpretation, and task-based support, which may help learners develop a foundational understanding of literary texts (Bustamante, 2022).

In contrast, the 7 lowest-rated indicators point to strategies that are present but less consistently emphasized. Encouraging students to compare texts with previously read materials recorded the lowest mean ($M = 2.88$, $SD = 0.75$), suggesting limited opportunities for text-to-text connections. Other lower-ranked strategies include asking students to predict story developments ($M = 3.00$, $SD = 0.83$), using group or class discussions to deepen interpretation ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 0.86$), encouraging students to express feelings or values related to the text ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 0.85$), incorporating moral lessons and values from texts ($M = 3.06$, $SD = 0.85$), explaining figurative and ambiguous language ($M = 3.20$, $SD = 0.82$), and relating textual themes to students' personal experiences ($M = 3.18$, $SD = 0.76$). While these strategies are still interpreted as occurring "sometimes," they are present but less consistently emphasized, indicating a need for more frequent incorporation into reading instruction. Observation results also revealed that many teachers struggle to implement engaging strategies and media suitable for reading instruction, with lessons often conducted without systematic planning and with missed opportunities to activate students' cognitive abilities through structured pre-reading, reading, and post-reading stages (Milah et al. 2025).

Overall, the findings indicate that, as perceived by the participants, teachers' strategies in teaching literature are primarily characterized by clear guidance and organized support. While these approaches appear to facilitate understanding and interpretation of texts, the relatively lower emphasis on comparative, discussion-based, and reflective strategies suggest potential instructional enhancements that may further support deeper literary appreciation.

4. What are the participants' levels of literary appreciation skills in terms of:
4.1 Textual Analysis;
4.2 Interpretation; and
4.3 Contextual Understanding?

Table 4 presents a summary of the participants' literary appreciation skills across three dimensions: textual analysis, interpretation, and contextual understanding. The overall mean score of 21.20 ($SD = 4.40$) of the 30 items in literary appreciation skills, when combined, falls within the high range, indicating that, as a whole, participants demonstrate a generally high level of literary appreciation, indicated as "Very Good". This suggests that learners can engage with literary texts in multiple ways, including understanding meaning, analyzing content, and relating texts to broader contexts. However, the relatively large standard deviation indicates performance variability, suggesting that while many students perform well, others exhibit weaker skills in specific dimensions. Archuleta (2025) similarly found that students demonstrated high literary appreciation skills across analysis, interpretation, and contextual dimensions, though some showed relative weaknesses in specific areas, while many performed proficiently overall, mirroring the results of this study, with generally strong performance and notable individual variation.

Table 4

Summary Table of Literary Appreciation Skills

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Textual Analysis	6.81	Good	1.75
Interpretation	8.03	Very Good	1.89
Contextual understanding	6.36	Good	1.87
Literary Appreciation Skill	21.20	Very Good	4.40

A closer examination of the individual dimensions reveals a differentiated pattern of strengths and areas for development. Interpretation obtained the highest mean score ($M = 8.03$, $SD = 1.89$), indicating a high level of performance interpreted as "Very Good". This signifies that participants are relatively proficient in constructing meaning from texts, making inferences, identifying themes, and responding to implicit ideas. Interpretation often emerges as a strong dimension in literature learning because it is frequently reinforced through classroom discussion, questioning, and response-based activities. Interpretation consistently emerges as a strength in literature learning, where students demonstrate proficiency in constructing meaning from texts, making inferences, identifying themes, and responding to implicit ideas through reinforced classroom discussions, questioning, and response-based activities (Pastera et al. 2024).

Textual analysis showed a moderate level of performance, rated “Good” ($M = 6.81$, $SD = 1.75$). This indicates that while participants can analyze textual features such as language use, structure, and literary devices to some extent, their skills in this area are not yet consistently advanced. Textual analysis demonstrates moderate competence among learners, who engage with textual features such as language use, structure, and literary devices to a satisfactory degree, yet require sustained instruction to achieve consistent advancement in these skills (Mbuh, 2024).

Contextual understanding obtained the lowest mean score among the three dimensions ($M = 6.36$, $SD = 1.87$), although it still falls within the moderate range indicated as “Good”. This finding suggests that participants experience greater difficulty in relating texts to broader social, cultural, historical, or personal contexts. Contextual understanding often requires learners to integrate background knowledge with textual meaning, a process that can be challenging without guided instruction. Contextual understanding represents the most challenging dimension in literature learning within a moderate performance range, as learners struggle to connect texts to wider social, cultural, historical, or personal contexts without explicit instructional scaffolding to bridge background knowledge gaps (Suganob & Oliva, 2021)

Taken together, the findings indicate that participants’ literary appreciation skills are strongest in interpretation, followed by textual analysis, and weakest in contextual understanding. This pattern aligns with the existing literature, which suggests that interpretive engagement is more readily developed through routine classroom practices, whereas the analytical and contextual dimensions require more intentional instructional design (Qassem & Majul, 2024). The overall high level of literary appreciation suggests that learners are generally receptive to literature-based activities and capable of engaging meaningfully with texts, while also highlighting the need for targeted support in specific dimensions to achieve a more balanced literary development.

Research Question 5. Are the participants’ reading motivation, reading habits, and assessment of their teachers’ strategy in teaching literature significantly influenced by their literary appreciation skills?

Ho1: The participants’ reading motivation, reading habits, and assessment of their teachers’ strategy in teaching literature are not significantly influenced by their literary appreciation skills.

Ho2: The participants’ reading motivation does not significantly influence their literary appreciation skills.

Ho3: The participants’ reading habits do not significantly influence their literary appreciation skills.

Ho4: The participants’ assessment of their teachers’ strategy in teaching literature does not significantly influence their literary appreciation skills.

Table 8 presents the regression analysis examining whether reading motivation, reading habits, and students’ assessment of teachers’ strategies in teaching literature significantly predict literary appreciation skills. The regression model is statistically significant ($F =$

11.189, $p < .001$), indicating that the predictors collectively influence literary appreciation. The model explains 18.5% of the variance in literary appreciation skills ($R^2 = 0.185$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.168$). The 81.5% residual variance in the study's regression model on literary appreciation skills indicates substantial unexplained variability beyond reading motivation, habits, and teaching strategies. Possible unaccounted factors include students' prior literary knowledge and background experience, which shape interpretive frameworks; language proficiency, particularly in nuanced textual analysis; socioeconomic status, which influences access to diverse texts and resources; peer interactions and collaborative discussions that foster critical perspectives; and digital literacy or technology integration in reading practices. Regression analysis by Zhang (2022) revealed that factors such as content attractiveness significantly predict students' engagement with literary works (as indicated by the R^2), yet substantial residual variability persists, attributable to unmodeled influences such as readers' prior knowledge and interpretive frameworks.

After controlling for the number of predictors, the Adjusted R^2 of 0.168 (16.8%) provides a more conservative, objective estimate than the raw R^2 of 0.185, helping prevent overestimation in smaller models like this one. It indicates the percentage of variance in literary appreciation skills explained by the predictors (reading motivation, habits, and teachers' strategies). This indicates that the model has a moderate predictive power and leaves room for other factors, as it explains 16.8% of the variability in results.

Table 5
Regression Analysis on the Influence of Reading Motivation, Habits, and Teaching Strategies in Shaping Students' Literary Appreciation Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	8.619	2.461		3.503	.001
Reading Motivation	3.456	.838	.379	4.123**	.000
Reading Habits	-.804	.626	-.117	-1.284	.201
Teaching Strategies	1.706	.733	.191	2.329*	.021
Residual Variance	-	-	81.5%		
Model Summary					
R = 0.430	$R^2 = 0.185$	Adj. $R^2 = 0.168$	F = 11.189**	p = .000	

**significant at 0.01 level

*Significant at 0.05 level

Although the proportion of explained variance is modest, this level is not unexpected in educational research involving affective and instructional constructs. Literary appreciation is widely theorized as a complex outcome shaped by cognitive, motivational, pedagogical, and sociocultural influences; thus, the present findings should be interpreted as partial but meaningful contributions rather than as a comprehensive explanatory model. On this basis, H_0 is rejected, with due caution regarding the model's scope. In other words, even if the results are statistically significant, the model's ability to explain literary appreciation

skills is limited, so the findings should be interpreted carefully, acknowledging that other factors not included in the model may also play a significant role.

Reading motivation emerged as a significant positive predictor of literary appreciation skills ($B = 3.456$, $\beta = 0.379$, $p < .01$), thereby rejecting Ho2. A unit increase in reading motivation results in a positive increase of 3.456 units in literary appreciation skills, as shown by the regression analysis. This means that for every point increase in motivation, students' ability to interpret and engage with literature improves significantly, underscoring the importance of fostering motivation to develop stronger literary skills. Interpreted through expectancy–value theory and engagement-based models of reading, this result suggests that students who value reading and are motivated to engage with texts are more likely to invest the cognitive and emotional effort required for interpretation, reflection, and aesthetic response, the core processes underlying literary appreciation. This finding contributes to the literature by showing that reading motivation remains a significant predictor of literary appreciation even when reading habits and perceived teaching strategies are simultaneously considered. In this sense, motivation appears to function not merely as a by-product of reading frequency or instruction but as an independent affective pathway through which students develop deeper relationships with literary texts. Over time, reading motivation becomes a more significant predictor of reading achievement, reinforcing the idea that motivation fosters deeper engagement and facilitates the development of reading and literary skills (Cubillos and Tronsoco, 2025)

In contrast, reading habits did not significantly predict literary appreciation skills ($B = -0.804$, $\beta = -0.117$, $p = .201$), Ho3 cannot be rejected. A cautious interpretation is that habitual reading, particularly when operationalized as frequency or routine, may not adequately capture the quality, intentionality, or interpretive depth of students' reading experiences. Reader-response theory emphasizes that literary appreciation develops through active meaning-making and personal engagement with texts, rather than through exposure alone. When motivational and instructional factors are statistically controlled, the unique contribution of reading habits appears limited, suggesting conceptual overlap or attenuation effects among these variables. In other words, it indicates that reading habits do not significantly contribute distinctive value to forecasting literary appreciation skills, even when students' enthusiasm to read and teachers' teaching strategies are considered within the statistical model. The study revealed that habits exhibited a weak, non-significant effect (beta = -0.117, $p = 0.201$), whereas motivation demonstrated a strong positive effect, and strategies. This indicates that habits may conceptually overlap with these factors, such as frequent academic reading being influenced more by interest or guidance than by mere routine, or that their impact diminishes when assessed in combination. However, it suggests that enhancing motivation and improving pedagogical techniques may be more effective than just encouraging increased reading frequency.

Teachers' strategies in teaching literature were found to significantly predict literary appreciation skills ($B = 1.706$, $\beta = 0.191$, $p = .021$), thereby rejecting Ho4. A unit increase in teaching strategies results in a 1.706 unit increase in literary appreciation skills. This indicates that enhancing teaching methods, such as incorporating more interactive or interpretive activities, directly boosts students' ability to engage with and appreciate

literature. From a sociocultural and instructional scaffolding perspective, this finding underscores the role of teachers as mediators of literary understanding. Instructional strategies such as guided discussion, interpretive questioning, contextualization of texts, and reflective activities may help students move beyond literal comprehension toward deeper literary interpretation and appreciation. Although the effect size is moderate, the result suggests that teaching strategies contribute meaningfully to literary appreciation, even after accounting for student-level motivational factors. This finding adds to the literature by reinforcing the complementary roles of instruction and motivation, rather than positioning them as competing influences. It also suggests that reading comprehension strategies employed by teachers, such as contextualization and reflective activities, contribute to the development of higher-level literary skills, reinforcing the idea that teaching strategies are a significant predictor of students' literary appreciation (Lagdaan & Sevilla, 2025)

In the multiple regression (Table 8), unstandardized betas (B) indicate the change in the literary appreciation score (out of 30) per 1-unit increase in the predictor, controlling for the others. Reading motivation has a strong positive effect ($B=3.456$, $p<0.01$); teaching has a positive effect ($B=1.706$, $p<0.05$); reading habits have a non-significant effect ($B=-0.804$, $p=0.201$), indicating limited unique contribution due to overlap. Overall, $R^2=0.185$ prioritizes motivation and instruction over habits. This finding aligns with broader assessment evidence indicating that higher-order reading outcomes are more closely associated with engaged and reflective reading practices than with time spent reading (Wang et al. 2022). The contribution of this result lies in its cautionary implications for both research and practice: encouraging students to read more frequently without attention to engagement and interpretive support may not be sufficient to enhance literary appreciation.

Taken together, the findings suggest that literary appreciation is more consistently associated with affective engagement and instructional mediation than with reading frequency alone. The contribution of this study lies in clarifying the relative influence of these variables within a single explanatory model, highlighting reading motivation as a dominant predictor, teaching strategies as a supportive instructional condition, and reading habits as a variable whose influence may depend on the quality of engagement rather than mere routine. At the same time, the modest variance explained signals the need for restraint in interpretation and points to directions for future inquiry. A prudent implication is that subsequent studies should incorporate variables more proximal to literary appreciation, such as interpretive strategy use, literary comprehension, language proficiency, and the nature of classroom discourse, and refine measures of reading habits to capture depth-oriented and reflective reading practices. For pedagogy, the findings suggest that efforts to enhance literary appreciation may be more effective when they focus on cultivating motivation and on employing purposeful literature-teaching strategies, rather than emphasizing reading frequency in isolation.

Research Question 6. Based on the study's findings, what action plan can be recommended?

An Evidence-Based Action Plan for Improving Literary Appreciation Introduction

This implementation plan is aligned with the MATATAG Curriculum of the Department of Education, which emphasizes foundational skills, meaningful engagement, and learner-centered instruction. Consistent with MATATAG principles, the plan prioritizes *quality of engagement, guided meaning-making, and contextualized learning* over increased task quantity. The interventions respond directly to the study’s findings, particularly the low levels of reading motivation and instructional strategies, and the non-significant influence of reading habits on literary appreciation.

School Improvement Aligned Action Matrix

Area 1 (Reading Motivation): Low Voluntary Reading and Limited Peer/Family Sharing

Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget)	Responsible Persons	Frequency
Low voluntary reading (<i>M</i> = 1.64)	Language & Literacy Foundations	Increase student engagement with literary texts Beyond class time	Encourage reading challenges with digital books, author talks, peer reviews, multimedia projects, and a recommendation box.	English teachers, librarian	Weekly
Limited peer/family sharing (<i>M</i> = 2.07–2.18)	Learner Engagement & Well-being	Promote social interaction around reading	Reading buddy system; brief in-class sharing of home reading experiences	English teachers, students, parents	Weekly

Area 2 (Reading Habits): Rare Engagement with Newspapers and Magazines

Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget)	Responsible Persons	Time Frame
Rare nonfiction reading (<i>M</i> = 1.82)	Critical & Applied Literacy	Expose students to real-world texts linked to literature	Use free online news articles related to themes in literary texts	English teachers	Weekly

Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget)	Responsible Persons	Time Frame
Limited magazine reading (<i>M</i> = 2.13)	Multiliteracies	Build familiarity with varied text types	Assign reflective responses using open-access digital magazines	English teachers	Monthly

Area 3 (Strategy in Teaching Literature): Infrequent Use of Text Comparison Strategies

Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget)	Responsible Persons	Time Frame
Weak text-to-text connections (<i>M</i> = 2.88)	Higher-Order Thinking Skills	Strengthen comparative reading skills	Engage students in a group discussion to compare and contrast key themes, characters, and writing styles from two different literary works, followed by a visual representation of the comparisons on a digital platform.	English teachers	Quarterly
Limited comparative analysis (<i>M</i> = 2.88)	Analytical & Interpretive Skills	Develop reasoning and evaluation skills	Guided oral comparisons before short written outputs	English teachers, students	Quarterly

Area 4 (Literary Appreciation Skill): Moderate Textual Analysis and Contextual Understanding

Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget)	Responsible Persons	Time Frame
Moderate textual analysis (<i>M</i> = 6.81)	Deep Comprehension	Improve close reading and interpretation	Teacher-led annotation using board/projected text; oral identification of literary elements	English teachers	Weekly
Moderate contextual understanding (<i>M</i> = 6.36)	Contextualized Learning	Strengthen links between text and context	Short teacher explanations of historical/cultural context followed	English teachers, students	Weekly

Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget) by guided discussion	Responsible Persons	Time Frame
Area 5: Reading Habits Not a Significant Predictor					
Low Area Addressed	MATATAG Focus Area	Objectives	Strategies / Activities (No Budget)	Responsible Persons	Time Frame
Limited impact of habits ($p = .201, \beta = -.117$)	Meaningful Learning	Shift emphasis from frequency to engagement	Incorporate think-pair-share activities, where students first reflect individually, then discuss with a partner, and finally share their insights with the class.	English teachers	Year round
Overreliance on exposure	Quality of Learning Experiences	Ensure all reading tasks promote thinking	Implement 'Exit Tickets,' where students write down one key takeaway or a question from the reading before leaving class, ensuring regular reflection and comprehension.	English teachers	Daily

Concluding Implementation Note

This MATATAG-aligned action plan does not call for an additional budget, as it demonstrates that improvements in appreciating literature are possible through instructional refinement without additional financial resources. Integrating interpretive practices, motivational supports, and guided instruction into regular English classes enables schools to target identified gaps while staying aligned with national curriculum priorities and practical school realities.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, literary appreciation may be more influenced by affective and instructional elements than by reading routines alone, at least in the context of this study, which is focused on Grade 11 learners. The data suggest that students' individual motivation to read and the scaffolding offered by their literature teachers contribute more strongly to developing literary appreciation over time than how often they actually read. This highlights purposeful engagement and guided interpretation as fundamental to literature classes, especially (I would argue) in contexts that may more objectify reading practices shaped by digital rather than print-based environments.

From a practical perspective, instructional efforts should target strategies that galvanize students' motivation and engagement with literary perspectives. Implementing more interpretive discussion, the contextual grounding of texts, and structured comparative opportunities for students as a regular practice of teaching may close gaps in higher literary skills. Book-lending programs run by the school that make reading material accessible, and careful pre-reading activities designed to help students tackle both contingencies, may further reinforce these strategies without straining schools for resources. This is particularly significant in Philippine secondary schools, where the time spent teaching and engaging learners seems to compensate for limited access to materials.

However, some limitations should be considered when interpreting these results. The research was restricted to a single school environment, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other educational settings. Moreover, the use of self-reported data carries the risk of response bias, and the limited explanatory power of the statistical model indicates that other important factors were not investigated. Future research could therefore examine more diverse samples and other learner and classroom characteristics, and adopt alternative methods of inquiry to further interpret the findings generated by this study.

Overall, the study makes a hesitant but constructive contribution by distinguishing the significance of motivation and instructional practices for literary appreciation and offering guidance for refinement while fostering further inquiry rather than sweeping conclusions.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered: For students, they may cultivate stronger voluntary home reading habits, such as logging short sessions weekly, to leverage their high motivation for better comprehension and critical thinking in literary appreciation. Form peer reading groups to boost emotional engagement and academic performance by sharing book recommendations regularly. For literature teachers, they may prioritize frequent text-comparison activities, such as Venn diagrams across paired texts, to address the lowest-rated strategy and deepen students' literary engagement; and integrate more student-led discussions on personal connections to texts to enhance motivation and classroom interaction. For school administrators, they may establish classroom lending libraries and fund digital nonfiction subscriptions to counter low print media habits and enhance evidence-based literacy programs, and allocate resources for teacher training on high-impact strategies, such as literary element discussions, to elevate overall school literacy. Finally, for future researchers, they may extend this work by testing interventions across diverse genres and grade levels, building on the significant influence of motivation and teaching strategies shown here, and by exploring the longitudinal effects of online reading habits on literary skills across varied cultural contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As stated in RA 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal data/information has been collected for valid purposes. Furthermore, the distributed and collected data had been coded to protect participants' identities. The names, cellphone numbers, and email addresses of the participants were not collected at the time they answered the form, in line with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). Instead of the participants name, the researcher assigned a unique code number, which has been written on the questionnaires and test papers; any list that links the participants' name to this code (if needed for coordination) were kept separate from the research data, accessible only to the researcher and authorized research team members, and has not been included in any analysis or report. All data collected were treated with strict confidentiality, and upon completion of the study and encoding, the soft copies were permanently deleted, while the hard copies were properly disposed of after the data acquired from the participants were fulfilled. Thus, the researcher secured an assent form from the research participants, and the informed consent of their parents/guardians was attached.

The Belmont Principles were strictly adhered to throughout the data-gathering process. This study found no significant risk; however, students did experience boredom or minor fatigue while completing the reading and literature test questionnaire. The researcher also ensured a comfortable, safe environment and refrained from eliciting compelling responses. Any adverse feelings that occurred during the scheduled sessions were communicated to their teacher and/or researcher for assistance and solutions. The following steps were assured the adherence to the Belmont principles of beneficence, justice, and respect for persons were strictly followed: to maintain beneficence, researchers analyzed and reduced any risks involved, clearly state risks and benefits in consent documents, and optimize the expected benefits of participation; to ensure justice, researcher selected participants through fair selection and exclusion processes, ensuring that risks and benefits are distributed equally without bias or abuse towards individuals who are vulnerable; and to maintain respect for persons, researchers conducted a significant informed consent process that ensures participants were aware of the study and voluntarily agreed to participate, while safeguarding their dignity and independence. There were no conflicts of interest associated with this study, and the researcher affirms that no personal, financial, or professional interests have influenced the conduct or outcomes of this research.

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